

Modifying the size of Nickel metallic particles by H₂/CO treatment in Ni/ZrO₂ methane dry reforming catalysts

Journal:	<i>ACS Catalysis</i>
Manuscript ID:	Draft
Manuscript Type:	Article
Date Submitted by the Author:	n/a
Complete List of Authors:	Caballero, Alfonso; University of seville, Inorganic Chemistry Gonzalez, Victor; CSIC Holgado, Juan; CSIC Pereñiguez, Rosa; CSIC Ternero, Fatima; CSIC

SCHOLARONE™
Manuscripts

Modifying the size of Nickel metallic particles by H₂/CO treatment in Ni/ZrO₂ methane dry reforming catalysts

Victor M. Gonzalez-Delacruz, Rosa Pereñíguez, Fatima Ternero, Juan P. Holgado and Alfonso Caballero*

Instituto de Ciencia de Materiales de Sevilla (CSIC-University of Seville) and Departamento de Química Inorgánica, University of Seville. Avda. Américo Vespucio, 49. 41092. Seville, Spain. caballero@us.es

Abstract

The effect of a reduction process with CO or H₂ on the size of nickel particles in Ni/ZrO₂ dry methane reforming catalysts have been studied by means of in situ XAS and DRIFTS spectroscopies. Our results clearly indicate that a high temperature treatment with CO increases the dispersion of the nickel metallic phase. XAS results have shown a lower coordination number of Ni in the sample treated with CO than that reduced with H₂. From the DRIFTS results, it can be established that, under the CO treatment, the formation of Ni(CO)₄ complexes corrodes the nickel particles, decreasing their size. The formation of these gas molecules occurs without measurable losses of nickel from the catalyst which maintains the same nickel content after the hydrogen or the CO treatment at high temperature. Therefore, this airborne nickel compound, by colliding with the zirconia surface, must deposit the nickel metal atoms around onto the support. This behavior is an evidence of an important interaction between nickel and zirconia surface as unlike other supports, there is no losses of nickel during the dispersion process on zirconia. Although different effects of CO on nickel catalysts have been previously described, we have found for the first time several experimental evidences demonstrating the whole redispersion phenomenon.

Keywords: Nickel catalysts, XAS, FTIR, DRIFTS, Dispersion, Dry methane reforming, Reduction with CO.

1. Introduction

Reforming of methane is at present one of the most important industrial reactions, partially due to the huge reserves of natural gas [1,2]. Nowadays, Ni-based catalysts continue as the best economic and performing catalytic systems for this kind of hydrocarbon reforming reactions [3-5], and in particular for the steam reforming of

1
2
3 methane, which has been proposed as the source for hydrogen production [6]. Beside
4 this reaction, the dry reforming of methane, using carbon dioxide as oxidant, has been
5 lately extensively studied as an alternative, even though it has been pointed out as
6 impractical for commercial hydrogen generation [7]. In spite of that, there is a great
7 potential in the application of CO₂ reforming of methane in environmental areas, such
8 as the elimination of CO₂ emissions from natural gas deposits or the utilization of these
9 two greenhouse gases for obtaining synthesis gas (CO/H₂) [8,9] which, in different
10 proportions, is extensively used in industrial processes as methanol synthesis,
11 hydrogenations or Fischer–Tropsch reactions [10].

12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19 However, these kinds of Ni-based materials are very sensitive to the coke
20 deposition during reaction, which hinders their use as a long term catalyst in industrial
21 applications. Several papers have stated that the dispersion, morphology and interaction
22 of the nickel metallic phase with the support strongly determine the catalytic
23 performances of these catalysts [11-14]. In general, it has been established the difficulty
24 in preparing Ni-based catalysts of appropriate dispersion and stability.

25
26
27
28
29
30 As fresh nickel catalysts usually present the oxide phase, a previous reduction
31 process is needed to obtain the catalytic active phase of nickel before performing the
32 reaction. This previous step, essential for obtaining an appropriate final dispersion of
33 the reduced metallic phase, is therefore one of the most important stages in the
34 preparation process. As the pretreatment of the catalysts with H₂ is the most common
35 process of reduction, Ni-based catalysts have been extensively studied during this
36 process showing in some cases the existence of strong interactions between the Ni
37 particles and the support [13,15]. On the other hand, a number of previous
38 investigations have shown that under certain conditions, CO corrosively interacts with
39 metallic nickel, causing changes on the metal particles sizes and even some nickel loss
40 from the catalyst surface [16]. This effect is especially relevant in hydrocarbon
41 reforming reactions, as beside hydrogen, CO is formed as a product. Sintering of the Ni
42 particles during treatments with CO has also been reported by some authors [16–19].
43 All these effects have been assumed to be caused by nickel transport from particle to
44 particle in the form of nickel sub/tetracarbonyls which migrate either on the support
45 surface or through the gas phase, leading to the metal particles growth. In this work, we
46 have studied the effect of two different processes of reduction, with H₂ or with CO, in
47 the metallic particle sizes of two different Ni/ZrO₂ catalysts active for the dry reforming
48 reaction of methane. The use of different characterization techniques, as XRD, SEM
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 and in situ XAS and DRIFTS, has allowed us to determine and compare the relative size
4 of the nickel particles achieved by the two different reduction processes.
5
6
7

8 **2. Experimental**

9 *Catalysts preparation*

10
11
12 Two different nickel loadings were used to obtain diverse particles size and
13 metal dispersions. A 26%wt Ni/ZrO₂ and a 3%wt Ni/ZrO₂ catalytic systems were
14 prepared as powder by impregnation of a monoclinic zirconia support with a nickel
15 nitrate solution (Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O from Aldrich). Zirconia support was synthesized via
16 forced hydrolysis [20] using an aqueous solution of ZrO(NO₃)₂·xH₂O (from Aldrich).
17 The powder was calcined at 850°C during 3 hours to prevent any change on the support
18 under reaction temperatures.
19
20
21
22
23
24
25

26 *Temperature Programmed Reduction (TPR)*

27
28 TPR experiments were done from room temperature up to 500 °C, with a heating
29 rate of 10 °C/min, holding temperature at 500°C for 1 hour. A thermal conductivity
30 detector (TCD), previously calibrated using CuO, and a mass spectrometer in line with
31 the TCD, calibrated with reference mixtures, were used to detect variations of reducing
32 agent concentration, and possible sub-products formation. A H₂/Ar mixture (5% H₂, 50
33 ml/min flow) was used for H₂-reduction, while reduction with CO was accomplished
34 with a 5% CO/He mixture. All the experimental conditions were chosen to assure that
35 no peak coalescence occurs [21].
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43

44 *Catalytic activity tests*

45
46 Reaction was carried out in a fixed-bed tubular reactor described elsewhere [22],
47 using 40 mg of catalysts between two pompons of quartz wool. Before reaction,
48 samples were reduced with CO or H₂ at 500°C during 1 hour. The CH₄ and CO₂
49 reactants were mixed at a ratio of 1 diluted in He (10:10:80 in volume). Samples were
50 heated from room temperature up to 750 °C at 1°C/min rate, held at 750 °C during 12 h,
51 and finally cooled down to room temperature in the same reaction mixture. Reactants
52 and products were analyzed by means of a gas chromatograph (Varian, CP-3800)
53 equipped with a thermal conductivity detector (TCD) and a Porapak Q packed column.
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

X-ray diffraction (XRD) and Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

1
2
3 X-ray diffractograms were recorded in a Panalytical XPert PRO device,
4 equipped with a X'Celerator Detector (active range of $2\theta = 2.18^\circ$), with a Bragg-
5 Brentano configuration, using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$). Diagrams were collected in the
6 range $2\theta = 20^\circ$ - 80° , with a step of 0.05° and an acquisition time of 80 s for each point.
7 To calculate the mean size of the crystalline particles of Nickel and nickel oxide by
8 Scherrer formula, X-ray diffractograms were also collected in the range of $2\theta = 35^\circ$ - 55° ,
9 with a step of 0.03° during 100 s each point. SEM images were obtained in a Hitachi S-
10 5200 microscopy equipped with a field emission filament, using an accelerating voltage
11 of 5 kV.
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20

21 *X-ray absorption spectroscopy*

22 X-ray absorption spectra (XAS) were recorded at the BM25 beam line (SPLINE)
23 of the ESRF synchrotron (Grenoble, France). The spectra were acquired in transmission
24 mode, using self-supported wafers of the Ni/ZrO₂ sample, in a modified commercial
25 infrared cell (Specac) able to work up to 800°C under controlled atmosphere [13]. XAS
26 spectra were collected at different temperatures during treatments of the samples.
27
28
29
30

31 In all cases the self-supported pellets were prepared using the optimum weight to
32 maximize the signal-to-noise ratio in the ionization chambers ($\log I_0/I_1 \approx 1$). Mass flow
33 controllers were used for dosing the gases to the cell. The composition of the gas
34 mixtures were similar to that previously used in the TPR experiment during the
35 hydrogen or CO reduction treatments. For energy calibration, a standard Ni foil was
36 introduced after the second ionization chamber (*I1*) and measured simultaneously.
37 Typical XAS spectra of Ni *K*-edge were recorded from 8200 to 9100 eV, with a variable
38 step energy value, with a minimum 0.5 eV step across the XANES region. Once
39 extracted from the XAS spectra, the EXAFS oscillations were Fourier transformed in
40 the range 2–11.0 \AA^{-1} . Spectra were analyzed using the software package IFEFFIT [23].
41 The theoretical paths for Ni–Ni and Ni–O species used for fitting the first coordination
42 shell of the experimental data were generated using the ARTEMIS program and the
43 FEFF 7.0 program [24]. The coordination number, interatomic distance, Debye–Waller
44 factor and inner potential correction were used as variable parameters for the fitting
45 procedures. Reference spectra for metallic Ni and NiO were recorded using standard
46 reference samples.
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

Diffuse Reflectance FTIR Spectroscopy (DRIFTS)

1
2
3 FTIR spectra were collected in a FTIR JASCO 6300 equipped with a Praying
4 Mantis DRIFTS cell, using a reaction chamber able to work up to 600°C under
5 controlled atmosphere. Mass flow controllers were utilized for dosing the gases to the
6 chamber, passing through the powder sample. FTIR spectra were collected in the range
7 of 4000-700 cm^{-1} with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} and 100 scans each. Spectra were acquired
8 at different temperatures during the “in situ” treatment of the sample.
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16

17 **3. Results and discussion**

18 *3.1. Temperature Programmed Reduction (TPR)*

19
20 The processes of reduction of the 26 wt% Ni/ZrO₂ catalyst with H₂ or CO were
21 studied by TPR experiments. According to the data obtained by these experiments,
22 depicted in Figure 1, the main reduction peaks are similar in shape, in both cases
23 centered around 400°C. The total H₂ consumption until 500°C roughly corresponds to
24 that expected for the complete reduction of the NiO phase to metallic Ni⁰. However,
25 when reduced with CO, the consumption of this reducing agent is much higher than
26 expected, mainly due to the presence of a wide new peak around 500°C. As a
27 subsequent oxidation treatment produces a large amount of CO₂, this peak must be due
28 to the decomposition of CO through the Boudouard reaction ($2\text{CO} \rightarrow \text{C} + \text{CO}_2$). In fact,
29 as it will be shown in section 3.4, the SEM images obtained after this CO treatment
30 confirm the presence of carbon in the CO-reduced catalyst, which is completely
31 eliminated by oxidation at 500°C.
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43

44 *3.2. Catalytic activity in the dry reforming reaction of methane (DRM)*

45 We have studied the catalytic performance of the catalysts after the two different
46 reduction processes, with H₂ or CO, respectively, in the DRM reaction. Both 26 wt%
47 Ni/ZrO₂ samples were studied for the DRM at 750°C using an GHSV of 1.5×10^5
48 L/(kg· h). First of all, it is important to remark that, as verified by SEM (images not
49 shown), under these reaction conditions, the carbon initially formed during the
50 reduction process with CO is eliminated through the inverse Boudouard reaction ($\text{C} +$
51 $\text{CO}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{CO}$) using the CO₂ from the gas mixture during the heating ramp. That means
52 that initially at 750°C, the catalyst surface must be free of carbon. As shown in Figure 2,
53 the catalytic performance strongly depends on the reduction treatment. Although the
54 initial activity is roughly the same in both systems, the catalyst previously reduced with
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 CO presents a much higher stability, especially after 9 hours in reaction conditions.
4
5 After 12 hours in reaction, this system loses just a 20% of the initial methane
6
7 conversion, while the same catalyst reduced in hydrogen loses a 40% of activity after
8
9 the same period of time. In all cases, the selectivity was stable, with values of ca 0.90
10
11 for the H₂/CO ratio, close to thermodynamic values for this reaction at that temperature.

12
13 As mentioned before, several factors can influence the catalytic activity of Ni-
14
15 catalysts in hydrocarbon reforming reactions. Between them, the dispersion of the
16
17 nickel metallic phase is one of the most important variables affecting the catalytic
18
19 performances. In order to characterize the size of the nickel metallic particles, we have
20
21 studied the catalysts by means of XRD and XAS after being reduced with hydrogen and
22
23 CO, respectively.

24 25 3.3. X-Ray Diffraction (XRD)

26
27 The crystalline phases present in the original and the reduced 26 wt% Ni/ZrO₂
28
29 catalyst were analyzed using X-Ray diffraction. Oxidized sample after CO reduction has
30
31 also been measured to compare with the original sample. XRD patterns of every sample
32
33 contain the peaks characteristic of the monoclinic structure of ZrO₂ (Figure 3), with no
34
35 relevant differences between them. The main peaks corresponding to the Ni phases
36
37 (oxidized and reduced) are also displayed in Figure 3. The peak at 2θ of 43.4° is
38
39 characteristic of the cubic structure of NiO phase (calcined and reoxidized samples),
40
41 while catalysts after CO or H₂ treatment present a peak at 2θ of 44.5°, corresponding to
42
43 the cubic structure of metallic Ni phase. No other nickel phases are detected by XRD
44
45 measurements.

46
47 The size of the particles has been estimated from these diagrams by applying the
48
49 Scherrer equation [25]. The crystalline size of the ZrO₂ phase is around 20nm for all the
50
51 samples, with no changes after the reducing and oxidizing treatments. This is not the
52
53 case for the Ni particles, where significant changes have been observed in the particle
54
55 sizes as a function of the reduction treatment. As it can be seen in **Table 1**, the original
56
57 nickel oxide particles present a diameter of 48nm. After reduction treatment, the size of
58
59 the CO reduced nickel particles has decreased to 32 nm (-33%), while the reduction
60
with hydrogen roughly maintains the initial size of the nickel particles. Moreover, this
effect seems to be permanent, as after re-oxidation of the CO-reduced sample, a similar
size (31nm) is obtained for the NiO particles, lower than the original ones.

3.4. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

In order to further figure out the effect of the treatment with CO decreasing the size of the metallic Ni particles, a study by scanning electron microscopy has been accomplished after the successive treatments with H₂, CO and oxygen. As shown in the SEM images included in Figure 4, the original sample present two different kinds of particles. The round shape particles, with a size around 20 nm that according to the XRD data must correspond to the ZrO₂ phase, and the bigger ones, with an octahedral shape, related with the NiO phase. After H₂ treatment at 500°C, the Ni particles appear rounded but with a similar or slight lower size that the original NiO phase. However, after CO reduction at 500°C, these octahedral particles evolved in smaller rounded entities, showing that the CO treatment corrodes the nickel particles, decreasing the size of the original crystallites. Besides, it is apparent the formation of carbon fibers over the catalyst, that confirming the decomposition of CO via the Boudouard reaction as previously deduced from the TPR results. After the reoxidation treatment with O₂ at 500°C, these carbon fibers disappear, without noticeable change in the shapes and sizes of the Ni/NiO particles, in agreement with the results obtained by XRD.

At this point, it must be noted that the quantitative analysis of the nickel content by ICP-MS after the reduction treatment with CO and subsequent oxidation at 500°C, shows the same nickel content on all the samples, meaning that no losses of this metal has occurred during the treatment with CO.

3.5. X-Ray Absorption Spectroscopy (XAS)

The Ni particles of the 26 wt% Ni/ZrO₂ system have also been characterized by in situ X-Ray Absorption during the reduction processes with CO and H₂ at 500°C. In both cases, the spectra were collected in situ, in contact with reactive gases, after cooling down to room temperature. Ni K-edge XANES spectra obtained after the different treatment are displayed in Figure 5, where also a Ni foil spectrum has been included as a reference. The original sample presents a white line and pre-edge features similar to the massive NiO compound used as a reference (not shown). Accordingly, the XANES spectra obtained after CO and hydrogen treatment roughly correspond to a metallic nickel phase, showing that the original NiO phase has been completely reduced to Ni⁰, in agreement with the TPR experiments (Figure 1) and with previous results on similar catalytic systems [13]. Even though an important carbon formation has been detected after CO treatment (Figure 4), no features from nickel carbides or related

1
2
3 species were detected in the XANES spectra [26]. The only remarkable difference
4 between these spectra is the slightly higher white line obtained for the CO reduced
5 sample, which must be due to the fact that the spectra has been collected at room
6 temperature, conditions allowing the surface adsorption of CO in the metallic nickel
7 particles, slightly modifying the electronic density of the metallic nickel atoms at the
8 particles surface. This interpretation is also confirmed with the EXAFS results shown
9 below.

10
11
12
13
14
15
16 The Fourier transformed (FT) functions obtained from the EXAFS oscillations
17 of the XAS spectra are presented in Figure 6 (without phase shift corrections). Once
18 again, the FT functions of the oxidized samples are typical for NiO systems, with two
19 main peaks below 3.5 Å. Also, those obtained after the reduction processes indicate the
20 presence of metallic nickel, confirming the nickel has been completely reduced after the
21 CO and hydrogen treatments. No peaks from oxidized nickel phases are detected.
22 Although some differences in the intensity of the main peak at 2.4 Å could be observed
23 between the samples reduced with CO or hydrogen, the fitting analysis shows similar
24 structural parameters for both systems. After these fitting results, included in Table 2, in
25 both cases the main peak centered at around 2.4 Å, corresponding to the first Ni-Ni
26 coordination shell of metallic nickel, yields 12 neighbors atoms at 2.49Å, so H₂ or CO
27 reduction give particles with the same coordination number (C.N.=12). The only
28 remarkable differences come from the Debye-Waller factors, slightly higher for the Ni
29 particles obtained after reduction with CO, which can be related with a slightly more
30 disordered structure. As the coordination number of the first shell in metals can be used
31 for determining the average particle size [27], this value of C.N.=12 indicates that the
32 Ni particles are in both cases larger than 10 nm, in agreement with the particle size
33 previously deduced from XRD. So, with such big particles, is not possible to determine
34 differences in size by XAS.

35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51 For this reason, we have prepared and characterized by in situ XAS, a similar
52 Ni/ZrO₂ catalyst but with a lower Ni content (wt. 3%). It is worthy to note that in this
53 catalyst no peaks from nickel phases could be observed by XRD, whether the nickel is
54 oxidized or reduced. Figure 7 shows the FT functions obtained from the EXAFS region
55 of the XAS spectra of this 3%Ni/ZrO₂ system before and after reduction with CO or
56 hydrogen. The visual inspection of these FT functions clearly shows as the H₂-reduced
57 sample presents a Ni-Ni coordination shell (centered at 2.36 Å without phase
58 correction) much more intense that the CO-reduced one. According to the parameters
59
60

1
2
3 obtained by fitting analysis (Table 3), these peaks correspond to a coordination number
4 of about 12 in the first case, but just 10 in the catalyst reduced with CO, indicating that
5 the average crystallite size of nickel is much larger when reduced with hydrogen. In
6 accordance with other authors [28-30], a C.N. of 12 is associated with particles larger
7 than 10 nm in size, while a C.N. of 10 corresponds to particle sizes around 4 nm. Thus,
8 these data are also in agreement with the behavior observed previously by XRD for the
9 catalyst with a higher loading of Ni, confirming that Ni particles after CO reduction
10 present a lower size than particles reduced with hydrogen. Therefore, the treatment with
11 CO strongly disperses the metallic particles of nickel from dispersion values lower than
12 10% (C.N.=12) to values around 20% (C.N.=10), showing that the dispersion effect
13 appers irrespective of the nickel content in the catalytic system.

14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23 At this time, it is important to remark that in both cases, these 3%Ni/ZrO₂
24 catalysts are almost inactive for the dry reforming of methane, reaching less than 10%
25 conversion of the hydrocarbon. This finding agrees with the well known fact that well
26 dispersed nickel particles are prone to coke formation, yielding less stable catalysts for
27 hydrocarbon reforming reactions (31,32). As it is also known that very big nickel
28 particles are also easily poisoning with coke, it means that, depending on the size range
29 of the particles, an increase in the dispersion of big particles could increase the
30 resistance to poisoning, as it seems to be the case for the 26 wt% Ni/ZrO₂ system.

3.6. Diffuse Reflectance FTIR Spectroscopy (DRIFTS)

31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41 The mechanism of this dispersion process can be understood from the FTIR
42 results obtained for the 3% wt. Ni/ZrO₂ sample, included in Figure 8. These spectra
43 have been obtained by in situ DRIFTS during the reduction treatment with CO. As
44 shown, when the sample is in contact at room temperature with 50 torr of CO, only gas-
45 phase CO bands are detected, which disappear after CO evacuation. By treatment with
46 CO, at the temperature of 400 °C a band centered at 2067 cm⁻¹ arises which according to
47 the literature, must be related with the formation of nickel carbonyl species [33-35].
48 This IR band is almost completely reversible, as it vanishes after evacuation at 400°C.
49 Also, it can be observed another band at 2187 cm⁻¹, which in accordance with Resini et
50 al. [36] can be assigned to CO adsorbed in Zr⁴⁺ Lewis acidic sites, or to carbonyls of
51 Ni²⁺-CO type. The 3wt% Ni/ZrO₂ sample previously reduced and the ZrO₂ used as
52 support have been measured in the same conditions (results not shown). In these
53 measurements the band at 2187 cm⁻¹ does not appear at 400°C, therefore indicating that

1
2
3 this band is probably associated to the adsorption of CO over oxidized Ni²⁺ species. As
4 shown, this band is not completely reversible after evacuating at 400°C, which agrees
5 with the known high stability of this Ni²⁺-CO species. The fact that this band is not
6 detected in the original oxidized sample can be related with the presence of surface
7 contamination (physisorbed water and carbonates species) covering the nickel particles.
8
9

10
11 The CO adsorption at 500°C must reduce the nickel, and produces just two
12 weak, reversible bands at around 2056 and 2088 cm⁻¹. After cooling down to room
13 temperature in the presence of CO, two intense bands could be easily detected: the first
14 one at 2089 cm⁻¹, which remains after evacuating the CO, and the second at 2056 cm⁻¹
15 almost completely reversible by evacuation. According to Mihaylov et al. [37], the
16 irreversible band at 2089 cm⁻¹ is related with CO adsorbed on dispersed Ni⁰, while the
17 reversible band at 2056 cm⁻¹ would be associated to physisorbed nickel carbonyl
18 species. As the ICP analysis have shown no losses of nickel from the catalyst during the
19 CO treatment, the formation of these Ni(CO)₄ could accounts for the dispersion process
20 of nickel, via formation of the tetracarbonyl complex and gas phase transfer to the
21 surrounding regions on the zirconia support. As these nickel carbonyl species do not fly
22 away from the catalyst through the gas phase, they must decompose over the support,
23 leaving the nickel species on the zirconia surface. This fact shows an important
24 interaction between the nickel entities and the zirconia support. As indicated in Scheme
25 1, the process must proceed by the initial surface reduction of the nickel oxide particles,
26 the subsequent formation of the tetracarbonyl complexes with these metallic atoms from
27 the surface, which through the gas phase, is readsorbed on the support nearby the
28 original particle. The final result is the corrosion of the original particle, in agreement
29 with the SEM images, and the decrease of the particle size. With hydrogen, the
30 reduction process is directly accomplished over the nickel oxide particle, resulting in a
31 metallic size similar to the original oxidized one.
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49

50 51 4. Conclusions

52
53 Our results clearly indicate that by comparing the reduction processes with H₂ or
54 CO at 500°C on Ni/ZrO₂ catalysts, the first one does not noticeably modify the size of
55 the original nickel oxide phase, while a similar reduction treatment with CO clearly
56 decreases the size of the particles, modifying the dispersion of the metallic nickel phase
57 in the catalyst, which explains the better catalytic stability of the CO reduced catalyst in
58 the methane dry reforming reaction. This different behavior during the reduction
59
60

1
2
3 **process** can be understood considering the formation of Ni(CO)₄ complexes during the
4 reduction with CO, which corrodes the nickel particles, decreasing their size and
5 depositing the metal atoms around onto the support. This gas phase process occurs
6 without measureable losses of nickel from the catalyst. This seems to be in
7 contradiction with the findings of others authors [16-19] that reported the sintering of
8 the nickel particles and/or the loss of metal from the catalyst during **other related**
9 **reactions as methanation of CO or methanol carbonylation**. These studies refer to
10 catalyst of nickel supported on silica, alumina or carbon. From our results, these
11 differences could be explained according to differences in the interaction of nickel with
12 the support surfaces. In our Ni/ZrO₂ catalysts, **as the nickel content do not decrease**
13 **during the CO treatment, it must indicate that the nickel carbonyl species do no fly**
14 **away but collide with the zirconia surface, where** the carbonyl species decomposes,
15 leaving the nickel atoms on the near surface and so, increasing the dispersion of the
16 metal particles **within the optimal range to improve the catalytic performance**.
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31

32 *Acknowledgments*

33 We thank the Ministry of Education and Science of Spain and Junta de
34 Andalucía for financial support (Projects ENE2007-67926-C02-01 and P07-FQM-
35 02520), the ESRF facility and the BM25 Spline beamline staff for their experimental
36 support.
37
38
39
40
41

42 *References*

- 43
44 [1] A.M. Gadalla, B. Bower, Chem. Eng. Sci. 43 (1988) 3049.
45 [2] J.R.H. Ross, A.N.J. van Keulen, M.E.S. Hegarty, K. Seshan, Catal. Today 30 (1996)
46 193.
47 [3] J.R. Rostrup-Nielsen, J.H. Bak Hansen, J. Catal. 144 (1993) 38.
48 [4] M.C.J. Bradford, M.A. Vannice, Appl. Catal. A 142 (1996) 73.
49 [5] Z. Zhang, X.E. Verykios, Appl. Catal. A 138 (1996) 109.
50 [6] J.N. Armor, Appl. Catal. A 176 (1999) 159.
51 [7] D. Lee, P. Hacıoğlu, S.T. Oyama, Top. Catal. 29 (2004) 45.
52 [8] W.D. Zhang, B.S. Liu, Y.P. Zhan, Y.L. Tian, Ind. Eng. Chem. Res. 48 (2009) 7498.
53 [9] V.M. Gonzalez-Delacruz, F. Ternero, R. Pereñíguez, A. Caballero, J.P. Holgado,
54 Appl. Catal. A: General 384 (2010) 1.
55
56
57
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 [10] M.C.J. Bradford, M.A. Vannice, *Catal. Rev. Sci. Eng.* 41 (1999) 1.
4
5 [11] J. Wei, E. Iglesia, *J. Catal.*, 224 (2004) 370.
6
7 [12] S. Tang, L. Ji, J. Lin, H.C. Zeng, K.L. Tan, K. Li, *J. Catal.* 194 (2000) 424.
8
9 [13] V.M. Gonzalez-DelaCruz, J.P. Holgado, R. Pereñíguez, A. Caballero, *J. Catal.* 257
10 (2008) 307.
11
12 [14] M.M. Barroso-Quiroga, A.E. Castro-Luna, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 35 (2010)
13 6052.
14
15 [15] A. Caballero, J.P. Holgado, V.M. Gonzalez-delaCruz, S.E. Habas, T. Herranz, M.
16 Salmeron, *Chem. Commun.* 46 (2010) 1097.
17
18 [16] W.M. Shen, J.A. Dumesic, C.G. Hill, Jr., *J. Catal.* 68 (1981) 152.
19
20 [17] M. Agnelly, M. Kolb, C. Mirodatos, *J. Catal.* 148 (1994) 9.
21
22 [18] G. Martra, H.M. Swaan, C. Mirodatos, M. Kermarec, C. Louis, *Stud. Surf. Sci.*
23 *Catal.* 111 (1997) 617.
24
25 [19] S. Yao, C. Yang, Y. Tan, Y. Han, *Catal. Commun.* 9 (2008) 2107.
26
27 [20] A. Caballero, J.J. Morales, A.M. Cordon, J.P. Holgado, J.P. Espinos, A.R.
28 Gonzalez-Elipse, *J. Catal.* 235 (2005) 295.
29
30 [21] P. Malet, A. Caballero, *J. Chem. Soc. Faraday Trans. I* 84 (1988) 2369.
31
32 [22] R. Pereñíguez, V.M. González-DelaCruz, A. Caballero, J.P. Holgado, *Appl. Catal.*
33 *B* 93 (2010) 346.
34
35 [23] M. Newville, *J. Synchrotron Rad.* 8 (2001) 322.
36
37 [24] B. Ravel, *J. Alloys Compd.* 401 (2005) 118.
38
39 [25] A.L. Patterson, *Phys. Rev.* 56 (1939) 978.
40
41 [26] S. Takenaka, Y. Shigeta, E. Tanabe, K. Otsuka, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 108 (2004) 7656.
42
43 [27] A. Jentys, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 1, (1999) 4059.
44
45 [28] A.I. Frenkel, C.W. Hills, R.G. Nuzzo *J. Phys. Chem. B* 105 (2001) 12689.
46
47 [29] J. de Graaf, A.J. van Dillen, K.P. de Jong, D.C. Koningsberger, *J. Catal.* 203
48 (2001) 307.
49
50 [30] J.T. Miller, A.J. Kropf, Y. Zha, J.R. Regalbuto, L. Delannoy, C. Louis, E. Bus, J.A.
51 van Bokhoven, *J. Catal.* 240 (2006) 222.
52
53 [31] S. Takenaka, S. Kobayashi, H. Ogihara, K. Otsuka, *J.Catal.* 217 (2003) 79.
54
55 [32] Y. Li, B. Zhang, X. Xie, J. Liu, Y. Xu, W. Shen, *J. Catal.* 238 (2006) 412.
56
57 [33] J.T. Yates, C.W. Garland, *J. Phys. Chem.* 65 (1961) 617.
58
59 [34] K. Hadjiivanov, M. Mihaylov, D. Klissurski, P. Stefanov, N. Abadjieva, E.
60 Vassileva, L. Mintchev, *J. Catal.* 185 (1999) 314.

1
2
3 [35] G. Poncelet, M.A. Centeno, R. Molina, Appl. Catal. A, 288 (2005) 232.

4
5 [36] C. Resini, T. Venkov, K. Hadjiivanov, S. Presto, P. Riani, R. Marazza, G. Ramis,
6
7 G. Busca, Appl. Catal. A: General 353 (2009) 137.

8
9 [37] M. Mihaylov, K. Hadjiivanov, H. Knözinger, Catal. Letters 76, No. 1–2 (2001).

10 11 12 13 Figure Captions

14
15
16
17 **Figure 1.** TPR profiles of 26 wt% Ni/ZrO₂ system, reduction with H₂ (upper profile)
18 and reduction with CO (down). Experiments were carried out from room temperature to
19 500°C at a heating rate of 10°C/min, holding the sample at 500°C during 1 hour.

20
21
22
23
24 **Figure 2.** CH₄ conversion in the reaction of dry reforming of methane (CH₄ + CO₂ →
25 2H₂ + 2CO) at 750 °C, using 26 wt% Ni/ZrO₂ catalyst after reduction treatments.
26 Catalyst = 0.04 g. CH₄ and CO₂ reactants were mixed at a ratio of 1 diluted in He
27 (10:10:80 in vol.). GHSV = 1.5×10⁵ L/kg·h.

28
29
30
31
32
33 **Figure 3.** X-Ray diffraction diagrams (XRD) of 26 wt% Ni/ZrO₂ system. Symbols
34 correspond with diffraction peaks of the monoclinic ZrO₂ (▽) and cubic structures of
35 NiO (■) and Ni⁰ (▲). A) Main Peak of cubic structure of NiO present in the calcined
36 and reoxidized samples. B) Main Peak of cubic structure of metallic Ni present in
37 reduced samples.

38
39
40
41
42
43 **Figure 4.** SEM images of the catalyst 26 wt% Ni/ZrO₂. a) Calcined; b) H₂ reduced
44 sample; c) CO reduced sample; c1) Backscattering image of c); d) Oxidized sample
45 after CO reduction.

46
47
48
49
50
51 **Figure 5.** In situ XANES spectra of the 26 wt% Ni/ZrO₂ sample submitted to the
52 different treatments. All the spectra have been collected after cooling down at room
53 temperature in contact with the gas phase.

54
55
56
57
58 **Figure 6.** Fourier transform functions of the EXAFS oscillations (without phase
59 correction) obtained for the 26 wt% Ni/ZrO₂ sample submitted to the different
60

1
2
3 treatments. All the spectra have been collected after cooling down at room temperature
4
5 in contact with the gas phase.
6
7

8
9 **Figure 7.** Fourier transform functions of the EXAFS oscillations (without phase
10 correction) obtained for the 3 wt% Ni/ZrO₂ sample submitted to the different reduction
11 treatments. All the spectra have been collected after cooling down at room temperature
12 in contact with the gas phase.
13
14

15
16
17 **Figure 8.** FTIR spectra of the 3 wt% Ni/ZrO₂ sample during reduction treatment with
18 CO. All the spectra have been collected at the indicated temperature, in contact with the
19 gas phase. Solid lines: Spectra under CO atmosphere (Gas mixture: 5% CO/Ar). Dash:
20 Spectra after CO evacuation.
21
22
23
24

25
26 **Scheme 1.** Schematic evolution of the shape of the nickel particles submitted to a
27 reducing treatment with CO. 1) NiO particle; 2) CO molecules react with Oxygen atoms
28 of NiO producing CO₂. 3) When the Particle is partially reduced, some CO molecules
29 form tetracarbonyls with nickel atoms, depositing the metal atoms around onto the
30 support. 4) Finally, metallic particles of Ni show a smaller size than the original particle
31 of NiO.
32
33
34
35
36
37

38
39 **Table 1.** Crystalline size of the NiO and Ni phases in the 26 wt% Ni/ZrO₂ system after
40 the indicated treatments, calculated from XRD results by applying the Scherrer
41 equation.
42
43
44

45
46 **Table 2.** Structural parameters for Ni obtained by fitting analysis of the EXAFS spectra
47 of 26 wt% Ni/ZrO₂ catalyst submitted to the indicated treatments.
48
49

50
51 **Table 3.** Structural parameters for Ni obtained by fitting analysis of the EXAFS spectra
52 of 3 wt% Ni/ZrO₂ catalyst submitted to the indicated treatments.
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

Table 1

26wt% Ni/ZrO ₂	Crystalline size (nm)	
	NiO	Ni
Calcined	48	--
H ₂ -reduced	--	46
CO-reduced	--	32
Oxidized after CO reduction	31	--

Table 2

26wt% Ni/ZrO ₂	Ni-Ni (Å)	C.N.	D-W factor (Å ² x10 ⁻³)	ΔE ₀ (eV)
H ₂ -reduced	2.48	12.0	5	5.8
CO-reduced	2.49	12.0	6	-6.8
Ni foil	2.48	12.0	5	6.7

Estimated errors: Interatomic distance, < ±0.02Å; Coordination number (C.N.), < ±10%

Table 3

3wt% Ni/ZrO ₂	Ni-Ni (Å)	C.N.	D-W factor (Å ² x10 ⁻³)	ΔE ₀ (eV)
H ₂ -reduced	2.50	11.8	6	-7.0
CO-reduced	2.49	10.2	9	-2.3
Ni foil	2.48	12.0	5	6.7

Estimated errors: Interatomic distance, < ±0.02Å; Coordination number (C.N.), < ±10%

Table of Contents (TOC) graphic

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

61x47mm (600 x 600 DPI)

62x48mm (600 x 600 DPI)

61x47mm (600 x 600 DPI)

56x39mm (600 x 600 DPI)

56x39mm (600 x 600 DPI)

55x39mm (600 x 600 DPI)

